

Relativity simplified using only time dimensions and a teleporting time traveller example

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Abstract

Minkowski 2D [1] and curved 3D [2] diagrams are widely used to understand relativity and represent space-time. They show how time slows down as a result of increasing speed and gravity. They are difficult to draw and understand. Here we show how simple 2D plots explain the concepts of relativity using only time dimensions. A teleporting time traveller example visually shows many properties of time including its curvature as we plot his/her journey through time. With existing diagrams these properties of time need to be derived and are still not evident. These plots will find applications in cosmology to explain the universe, understand time under quantum mechanics and nature of light under electromagnetism. It simplifies relativity, which is the most misunderstood subject in physics. Most important impact it will have is on how everyone in general perceives our universe and understands time.

Keywords: theory of relativity, space-time diagrams, time dimension, time travel, teleportation

1 Introduction

Minkowski 2D diagrams [1] represent space-time with light cones that show regions of past and future where we can physically move through time. Regions outside these cones are faster than light and cannot be physically traveled. A moving person and a stationary observer are needed to understand how time is affected from each one's point of view. Speed of the observer and his time dilation need to be calculated using Lorentz transformation to plot these diagrams. Calculations of the time dilation value is part of the special theory of relativity [3].

3D curved space-time [2] is used to represent curvature of space, popularly represented with funnel spaced wells for gravity of earth, solar system, black holes and wormholes. Plotting and understanding the curvature of space is beyond the common man's skill-set. It also gives the impression that only gravity causes curvature of space-time and not the speed of a moving object. Gravitational time dilation, part of general theory of relativity [4], needs to be calculated to plot curved space-time that restricts it to the world of physicists.

Time dilation values can be directly used to plot space-time diagrams, irrespective of the method used to calculate it. We use these values to first plot a simple two region space-time diagram, then we show how we can plot multiple regions of space-time on a single plot. A time traveller's path is plotted on this diagram that shows how his or her time is affected when teleporting between these regions. This simple diagram helps us understand the core concepts of theory of relativity [3, 4].

2 Methods

According to the theory of relativity, time slows down the faster we travel compared to a stationary observer. Further, the more the gravity, the more the time slows down. This slowing down property of time, called time dilation, can be summarized as below:

1. Time is relative. Time dilation is an effect experienced by a person in one space-time region relative to a person in another region.
2. Time dilation effectively means Time passes slower for one person compared to another. Conversely, time passes faster for one person compared to another.
3. Time can be infinitely slow or fast depending on the speed or gravity at different regions of the universe.
4. Time does not stop and it moves only in forward direction.

2.1 Plotting space-time regions

Time is relative, so time of one person can be easily plotted against the time of another person. This is shown in the plot at fig.1.

Fig. 1 Time Traveler's diagonal path between space-time regions

In fig.1, time on earth moves at a faster rate of 1 year for every 1 second on planet X. Journey of the time traveller is plotted on this diagram. Imagine you are the time traveller:

1. You teleport to planet X from earth.
2. You spend 1 second there and teleport back to earth.
3. You spend 1 year on earth and again teleport to planet X.
4. You spend 1 more second there and return back to earth.

Following can be observed in the fig.1:

1. **Time dilation:** 3 seconds of planet X are 3 years on earth, but the journey time for you was 1 year and 2 seconds.
2. **Journey to the past:** You cannot not travel into past on planet X, no matter how many times you teleport to that planet, even though time runs slow on the planet. You always comes to the present moment at the planet.
3. **Journey to the future:** You cannot travel into the future no matter how many times you teleport back to earth from planet X, even though time runs faster on earth. You always come to the present moment on earth.
4. **Time Travel:** You do experience coming into past on planet X and into future on earth. But it is just your perspective.
5. **Lines of simultaneity:** The diagonal path you trace while you teleport, show simultaneous events at the present moment on these planets, even though time passes at different rates.

This diagram is easy to plot even by hand and do not require time dilation calculations. The first time you teleport is a single point at origin which could not be adequately represented.

Fig. 2 Time traveler path on two region parallel space-time diagram

2.2 Two-region parallel space-time

Improving on the previous diagram, we plot the two regions, earth and planet X horizontally parallel to each other in fig. 2. This seems a natural representation for parallel worlds.

These lines represent time passing from past to future from left to right, similar to how we experience time. It also clearly indicates an important property of time that it moves only in forward direction at a fixed rate for each space-time region.

Vertical parallel lines represent lines of simultaneity, events occurring at the same moment for these regions.

Fig.2. now represent the same plot as fig 1. As you teleport from earth to planet X, it shows separate origin points on independent x-axis for both regions. You follow the same earlier path. We see that you spend 1 year and 2 second teleporting between the planets, while 3 seconds pass for planet X and 3 years for earth.

This diagram resembles an anticlockwise 90° rotated Minkowski space-time diagram [1]. Space dimensions are collapsed as movement in x, y and z directions are independent for these region. So, there is no space-time light cone, as light cannot reach from one region to another. There is no past or future light cone for each region, just a single line of time going past to future. There is no separate stationary and moving observer. You are the only observer who teleports between earth and the other planets.

2.3 Plotting multi-region space-time diagrams

Fig. 3 Multi-region space-time showing time traveller path

From two region space-time diagrams we can easily scale up to add multiple space-time regions. Fig.3 shows multiple space-time regions plotted as lines parallel to each other. Time passes from left to right, from past to future, represented by multiple parallel x-axis. Current time is represented with the central vertical line at 0 seconds.

Time dilation rate for each region is shown along the y-axis. Path of earth through one dimensional time is represented by a central horizontal line. Time dilation at earth is 1 second. So time at earth passes at one second per second. The more there is time dilation, the slower the time passes on the planet. This is represented by planets x1 and x2 having slower time dilation rate plotted below earth. Planets y1 and y2 with time passing faster than earth are shown with parallel lines above earth. They have inverse values of time dilation. There is no zero or infinity value for time dilation in the diagram, which could be on the extreme top and bottom respectively on y-axis. There is no zero value as time never stops. There is no infinity value, as we can plot any higher value for time dilation.

The time dilation values can be calculated using formula from special and general theory of relativity [3, 4], which are given in section 2.5. However, the purpose of these diagrams is to use time dilation values directly without getting into how it is calculated.

We again plot the path as you teleport between the planets:

1. From earth, you teleport to planet x2, spend 1second/100years, a minute fraction of a second, and return to earth.
2. You spend 1 second on earth and teleport to planet y2, spend 100years there and return back to earth.
3. You aged 100 years, 1 second and a fraction of a second during this period.
4. Meanwhile, a fraction of a second passes on planet x2, 3 seconds on earth and 300years on planet y2.
5. You experience coming back to the past on earth after completing your journey.
6. But time has still moved ahead on all these planets at different rates.

Fig. 4 Multi-region space-time showing time traveller path

2.4 Curved multi-region space-time

The plot in fig. 3 has a unit scale grid and is easy to plot. However, when we scale space-time regions to represent their comparative time, we find that time is curved. This is illustrated in fig. 4. It shows time dilation on y-axis as in earlier plot. Horizontal lines are parallel worlds with time moving from past to future at different rates. Curved lines are lines of simultaneity, events occurring at the same time at any given moment. Looking at the diagram, we can conclude that the curvature of space-time is due to the curvature of time. You follow the same path as in fig.3, as you teleport between the planets.

1. You teleport from earth to planet x3, spend 1/300years there and return back to earth.
2. You spend 1 second on earth and teleport to planet y3,
3. You spend 100 years there and return back to earth.

As you trace your path on the curved time, you can now clearly see yourself traveling into the future and past. But time has passed uniformly ahead at each of these planets. The experience of traveling into future and past is created only when you return back to the same planet from a planet with significant faster or slower time dilation rate. This is a true paradox, where you have actually done time travel but there is no real time travel. The regions are purposely plotted in the order of changing time dilation to resemble the natural curvature of space-time as a result gravity. However, as these regions of space-time are independent, the curvature will be distorted if we re-order the regions. This can be helpful to understand our universe with regions of varying space-time.

2.5 Set of 8 formulas that go along with diagrams

The y-axis in above plots show time dilation rate for each space-time regions represented by x-axis. Below are 8 formulas in table 1 and table 2, where we use time dilation values and get time dilation values back from speed and gravity of the reference planets where you teleport.

Table 1 Formulas we use where time moves slower for reference planet

Sr	Function	Formula	Input	Output	What the output says
1	Use Lorentz Factor	$\frac{v}{c} = \sqrt{1 - \frac{1}{t^2}}$	$t = 100 \text{ sec}$	$v = 0.99995 \times c$	The object is moving at 99.995% speed of light at time dilation of 100
2	Get Lorentz Factor	$t = \frac{1}{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}$	$v = 0.99995 \times c$	$t = 100 \text{ sec}$	We get time dilation of 100 at 99.995% speed of light
3	Use Gravitation Time dilation factor	$\frac{M}{r} = \left(1 - \frac{1}{t^2 \times \frac{c^2}{2G}}\right)$	$t = 100 \text{ sec}$	$\frac{M}{r} = 6.7324 \times 10^{26} \text{ Kg/m}$	The object has mass and radius ratio $6.7324 \times 10^{26} \text{ Kg/m}$ at time dilation of 100
4	Get Gravitation Time dilation factor	$t = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{M}{r} \times \frac{2G}{c^2}}}$	$\frac{M}{r} = 6.7324 \times 10^{26} \text{ Kg/m}$	$t = 100 \text{ sec}$	For the object with mass and radius ratio $6.7324 \times 10^{26} \text{ Kg/m}$ we get time dilation of 100

Where, t = rate of time dilation in seconds, v = velocity of moving body, M = Mass of star/planet, r = radius of star/planet constants: c = speed of light G = Gravitational constant

Table 2 Formulas we use where time is faster for reference planet

Sr	Formula Name	Formula	Input	Output	What the output says
1	Use Lorentz Factor	$\frac{v}{c} = \sqrt{1 - t^2}$	$t = 100 \text{ sec}$	$v = 0.99995i \times c$	Imaginary speed indicates, we the observer, are moving faster than the reference object.
2	Get Lorentz Factor	$t = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}$	$v = 0.99995 \times c$	$t = \frac{1}{100} \text{ sec}$	Inverse time dilation (less than one) indicates we are moving faster than the reference object.
3	Use Gravitation Time dilation factor	$\frac{M}{r} = \left(1 - \frac{1}{t^2} \times \frac{c^2}{2G}\right)$	$t = 100 \text{ sec}$	$\frac{M}{r} = -6.7324 \times 10^{26} \text{ Kg/m}$	The negative mass and radius ratio indicates we are at lower gravity than the reference object.
4	Get Gravitation Time dilation factor	$t = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{M}{r} \times \frac{2G}{c^2}}}$	$\frac{M}{r} = 6.7324 \times 10^{26} \text{ Kg/m}$	$t = \frac{1}{100} \text{ sec}$	Inverse time dilation (less than one) indicates we are at lower gravity than the reference object.

Where, t = rate of time dilation in seconds, v = velocity of moving body, M = Mass of star/planet, r = radius of star/planet constants: c = speed of light G = Gravitational constant

We have used 100 secs as time dilation rate in above formulas. Even at 99.995% of speed of light, we get time dilation of 100 seconds (one minute and 40 seconds) only for every one second. We cannot **scale up** the time dilation values much as we are already near speed of light. We further need to **stretch** the time dilation into a longer period to make better sense of it or to experience time travel. For eg. in one year, 100 years would have passed for a moving person at a time dilation of 100. This scaling and stretching of time are in-built in the above diagrams.

3 Results

While relativity is considered difficult, it is mostly misunderstood. These diagrams help clear myths about time. The first chart at fig.1 is a two-region plot showing the relativity of time among them. The second chart at fig.2 showed a more natural graph showing parallel worlds and time moving forward for each world from left to right at different rates. Then we progressed to add more parallel worlds in fig.3, which depict our universe as multi-region space-time. Using different scales for different rates of time dilation in fig.4, we get the property of curvature of time.

Following are some of the benefits of these diagrams:

1. They are easy to plot even by hand.
2. They depict time dimensions as we experience it
3. They reveal the nature of time visually
4. They show curvature due to time dimension
5. scaling up/down and stretching of time in diagrams helps understand time travel very well
6. Separates time dimension from space-time diagrams

These are some of the laws of time and time travel that come out from the diagrams:

1. Time is relative.
2. Time does not stop and moves uniformly in forward direction.
3. There can be infinite time dilation among the planets (and other stellar objects in universe).
4. Though time passes at different rate, the present moment is always the same everywhere.
5. A time traveler will experience going into the future.
6. He can travel into the future as far as he wants.
7. He will experience going into the past.
8. He cannot go into the past the time where he came from.
9. He always reaches in the present time of that planet.

4 Discussion

The need for these diagrams arose out of our earlier manuscript [5, 6], in which we have introduced the time traveller example to simplify relativity. These diagrams will further help visualise the time travel experience. Minkowski space-time diagrams [1] do not explain time travel well, creating a unresolved paradoxes [7]. Being based on

time dimensions only, the diagrams in this manuscript complement and not replace Minkowski diagrams [1]. Though they are simple to draw by hand, on computer we struggled plotting multiple x-axis for different regions of space-time. We settled with using grid lines or plotting lines for space-time regions to show multiple space-time regions. Books like, “A brief history of time” [8] have been dedicated to understanding and explaining the concept of time. Our article helps ask and answer many similar questions on time. Below we discuss different contexts in which we often try to understand time.

1. **Relativity [3, 4]:** We get the concept of space-time from relativity. However, we are now able to relate unconnected regions and use only time dimensions.
2. **Time travel paradoxes [7]:** A lot of efforts have gone into creating and resolving time travel paradoxes, like the famous grandfather paradox. The diagrams in this manuscript clearly show that there are no paradoxes to be resolved. There are no time loops or going forward or back in time.
3. **Speed of Light [9–11]:** Under special theory of relativity, the speed of a moving person observed by a stationary observer is always equal to the speed measured by the moving person for himself with his distance contracted and time dilated. In other words both agree on the speed of a moving person. In that case, we should know time dilation at the speed of light or our measurement of speed of light is incorrect. This could be due to us trying to understand time using speed of light, which itself is dependent on time. What is the fixed speed of light for us, could be different time dilation experienced by particles on the electromagnetic spectrum traveling at different speeds.
4. **Quantum Mechanics [12]:** We believed[5] that Quantum entangled particles would not remain entangled in a highly time dilated system. However, these diagrams clearly show the lines of simultaneous events. So, an instant at one place

could be the 100th year at another place, so quantum particles can remain entangled even under these systems. It could also mean a particle changes state every instant and the other particle doesn't change its state for 100s of years.

5. **Closed time like curves [13]:** Closed time like curves (CTCs) are trajectories in space-time that effectively travel backwards in time. Whether CTCs are supported by laws of physics is still debatable. These diagrams clearly indicate that traveling back in time is not permitted under relativity. They also indicate it may not be permitted even under Quantum Mechanics.
6. **Unified theory of gravity [14]:** We have properties of time that are independent of speed and gravity. These properties of time seem to be universal. This unified theory of time, could be the first step towards unified theory of gravity.
7. **Big bang theory [15]:** The age of the universe and the rate of expansion of the universe are in terms of time as we measure it. This article clearly indicates that we have so far been dealing in a very small range of time dilation values. We can model our universe using only time dimensions to get alternate perspective on age and rate of expansion of universe.
8. **Black hole [16] and Dark Matter [17]:** Like Newton's laws of motion are perfectly valid under local space-time, theory of relativity should be perfect up to the speed of light. Beyond that we may need another set of laws that define time, probably from quantum mechanics or electromagnetism or both. Using time dimension only could help us understand black hole and dark matter.
9. **Multiverse [18]:** Laws of motion do not make sense in unrelated space-time. However, time remains relative even in unconnected space-time regions as mentioned in the article. If multiverse does exist, they would share the same lines of simultaneity with our universe.

This article [19] we came across, tries to overcome the limitations of theory of relativity and provide explanations for mysteries of time using different geometry than

our article. It uses Euclidean Relativity (ER) and tries to solve 15 mysteries similar to above purely geometrically.

5 Conclusion

The diagrams in this article use only time dimensions, as against space-time diagrams that are popularly used to understand relativity. These are easy to plot. They scale well to higher time dilation values. They explain the properties of time that are universal in nature. They can help unravel many mysteries of the universe. They enable us to ask more scientific and philosophical questions about the universe. However, the primary purpose of this manuscript is to make the theory of relativity available to everyone.

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